

ISic0981

I.Sicily inscription 0981

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. []

1. υἱὸς Παύλου

2. [ζή]σας ἔτη ὀκτώ

3. [---] ἀνεπαύσατο

4. [---]ιου Θεοδω

5. [---]Ἀων δεκα

6. [---]ωφιτεσσἈ

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492607

EDCS 39102134

PHI 140458

PHI 331420

Bibliography

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